

A Study on Employee Welfare Measure at Vimpro Tech Puducherry

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ABSTRACT

The Employees welfare measure is a burning issue all over the world. Employee's welfare requires everything from service, facilities and benefits that are provided or done by an employer for the advantage or comfort of an employee. A study on employee's welfare measure aimed to find how employee's welfare measures in the organization encourage them to increase productivity and performance. The total population for the study is 140 and the sample size is 100. The type of sample design used for the study is simple random sampling. Primary and Secondary data was used for the study primary data was collected by using questionnaire and secondary data was collected from books, journals and company records. The gathered information is critically analyzed by using various statistical tools like chi square test and Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation. From the study, it was found that there is significant association between employee welfare measure and self-efficacy of employees and by using chi square test it was found that there is significant association between employee welfare measure and work performance of employees.

KEYWORDS: Employee welfare measures, self-efficacy, performance and productivity

How to cite this paper: R. Mohanapriya | G. Allwyn | T. Dhinakaran "A Study on Employee Welfare Measure at Vimpro Tech Puducherry" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-6, October 2019, pp.533-535, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29163.pdf>

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I. INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in the field of Science, Information Technology, Management etc., increased the scope of Personnel Management. The attitude of Management and Employees' towards each other has changed to a great extent. Employee Welfare is an important factor of Industrial relations and with the growth of Industrialization; it has acquired an added importance (Ravi& Raja 2016).

Employee welfare is a term including various services, benefits and facilities offered to employees by the employers. The welfare measures need not be monetary but in any kind/forms. This includes items such as allowances, housing, transportation, medical insurance and food. Employee welfare also includes monitoring of working conditions, creation of industrial harmony through infrastructure for health, industrial relations and insurance against disease, accident and unemployment for the workers and their families. Through these generous benefits the organization makes life worth living for employees. Welfare includes the activities that is done for the improvement and comfort of employees and is provided over and more than the wages. Welfare measures helps in maintaining the morale and motivation of the employees high so as to retain the employees for longer periods. This welfare need not be in monetary terms but in any kind/forms. Employee welfare includes monitoring of working conditions, creation of industrial harmony through infrastructure for health, industrial relations and insurance against disease, accident and unemployment for the workers and their and families.(Manasa & Krishnanaik 2015)

II. Objectives of the study

1. To find the satisfaction level of employees towards the welfare measures provided at vimpro tech company Puducherry.
2. To find the most influencing factor of employees welfare measures vimpro tech company Puducherry.
3. To find the significant association between employees welfare measures and self-efficacy of employees
4. To find the relationship between employees welfare measures and employees work performance.

III. Hypotheses of the study

1. H0: There is no significant association between employee's welfare measures and self-efficacy of employees.
2. H0: There is no relationship between employees welfare measures and employees work performance.

IV. Review of Literature

Ravi & Raja(2016) Labor Welfare Measures prove to be an important factor when compared to the other factors in the organization. When these measures are not provided to the fullest extent the workers self-interest and motivation decreases and their dedication to the work may declines. So, the task of the personnel manager becomes challenging and it imposes him to introduce the various employee welfare measures in the organization. These measures operate to neutralize the harmful effects to large scale industrialization and urbanization. Thus, these measures an organization are one of the factors for the workers to stay within the organization and to work towards success of the organization and this has been evident in this organization.

Lalitha(2014) Human resource plays an important role in any organization .employee welfare facilities are concern to this department, if the employee happy with welfare facilities then only the productivity of that organization can be increased. Based on the study of Employee Welfare Facilities in IT industry it is clear that the companies are very keen in the promoting all the welfare facilities provided by IT industries.

Usha Tiwari(2014) the study of Employees welfare schemes and its impact on employees' efficiency at Vindhya Telelinks Ltd. Rewa appear good. The average mean score and percentage score of the overall of 22 items has been computed at 3.64(66%). As per the study it is observe that VTL Rewa (M.P.)is provided various facilities to the employees and also follow the rules and regulation of state and Indian Government. The management required to provide good facilities to all employees in such way that employees become satisfied about employee welfare facilities. It increases productivity as well as quality and quantity. Therefore there is necessity of making some provision for improving the welfare facility through that employees will become happy, employees performance level become increase. It leads to improve favorable effects of profitability and products of the organization. At last it can be conclude that the employee welfare facilities provided by the company to employees are satisfied and it is commendable, but still of scope is there for further improvement. So that efficiency, effectiveness and productivity can be enhanced to accomplish the organizational goals.

Bharathiand Padmaja (2018) after analyzing the whole situation the researchers concludes it is proved that the Employees welfare activities are sufficient and effective for

the employees of LIC. The researcher reached with this conclusion after thorough the study of all the aspects of Employee welfare activities is pruning to job satisfaction and that leads to employee engagement. The employee of LIC was highly engaged and they are producing as according to the requirement and the mission statement of the company. The very important observation is all the employees of LIC were strongly connected to the objectives and their commitment towards productivity is very high.

Rajkur(2014) among the all, human being is the finest one, who needs skills, talents, attitudes, motivation, career planning and to deliver goods and services in time with the facilities of Labor Welfare Measures and Social Security. Employees are highly perishable, which need constant welfare measures for their up gradation and performance in this field. In India, service sector is a leading sector, which generates more employment, needs welfare measures for their improvement. The welfare facilities help to motivate and retain employees. Most of the welfare facilities are methods of hygienic among workers are motivated by providing welfare measures .This ensures employee satisfaction result in increased efficiency.

V. Research methodology

A research design is a plan that specifies the objectives of the study, method to be adopted in the data collection, tools in data analysis and hypothesis to be framed. The sample for the study is 100 is taken for the study. The sampling technique followed in the study is simple random sampling. The study was based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected form the employees working in vimpro tech. The statistical tool correlation and chi square is used in this study.

VI. Analysis and Interpretation

Table1 Frequency distribution of employees

S. NO	Employees profile		Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	60	60
		Female	40	40
		Total	100	100
2	Salary	Below 10000	10	10
		10000-20000	33	33
		20000-30000	26	26
		30000-40000	14	14
		Above 40000	17	17
		Total	100	100
3	Marital status	Married	70	70
		Unmarried	30	30
		Total	100	100
4	Age	Below 20	6	6
		20-30	27	27
		30-40	30	30
		40-50	16	16
		Above 50	21	21
		Total	100	100
5	Experience	Below 5	23	23
		5-10	38	38
		10-15	22	22
		15-20	8	8
		Above 20	9	9
		Total	100	100

6	Qualification	SSLC	13	13
		Diploma	19	19
		UG	27	27
		PG	18	18
		Others	23	23
		Total	100	100

Source: primary data

The above table show that 60% of the respondents are male and 40% of the respondents are female. 10% of the respondents are getting below 10000, 33% of the respondents are getting 10000-20000, 26% of the respondents are getting 20000-30000, 14% of the respondents are getting 30000-40000 and 17% of the respondents are getting above 40000 salary. Nearly 70% of the respondents are married 30% respondents are unmarried. From the table the study shows that 6% of the respondents are in the age group of below 20, 27% of the respondents are in the age group of 20-30, 30% of the respondents are in the age group of 30-40, 16% of the respondents are in the age group of 40-50 and 21% of the respondents are above 50 and most of the respondents are under graduates.

Table2 shows employee’s welfare measures and employees work performance

Sample size	Factor 1	Factor 2	Calculated value	Interpretation
100	Employee welfare measures	Employee work performance	0.078	Low degree of positive correlation

Source: primary data

From the above table r value is 0.0708 which shows a low degree of positive correlation. So we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis and it was found that there is relationship between employee welfare measures and employee work performance.

Table3 shows employee’s welfare measures and Self-efficacy of employees

Employees welfare measure & self-efficacy	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Low	0	0	0	0
Moderate	12	65	9	86
High	4	5	5	14
Total	16	70	14	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table Chi square value (calculated) = 9.824, p-value is 0.04 which is less than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It was found that there is significant association between employee welfare measures and self-efficacy of employees.

VII. Discussion and Conclusion

Welfare includes anything that is done for the comfort and improvement of employees and is provided over and above the wages. Welfare helps in keeping the morale and motivation of the employees high so as to retain the employees for longer duration. The study on Employee welfare measures at vimpro tech company Puducherry concluded that the employees are satisfied with the welfare measures provided in the organization and the satisfaction level of employee welfare measures towards vimpro Tech Company is moderate. It was found that the most influencing factor in vimpro tech company Puducherry is transport facility and the company has to improve its working environment by providing sufficient clean drinking water. By using Chi-Square, it was concluded that there is significant association between employee welfare measures and self-efficacy of employees. By using correlation it was also concluded that there is relationship between employee welfare measures and work performance.

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